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Literally norms and speech culture

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Annotation

This article is about information about literary norms and speech culture.

Key words: standard, standard forms, spelling, accent, pronunciation, punctuation, lexical, grammatical, stylistic, standard in word groups, conjugation, word order, speech defects - defects in oral and written speech, barbarisms, dialectisms, vulgarisms, slangs, violation of stylistic, orthographic and punctuation norms.

Literary language is a standardized, polished, redeveloped form of the national language based on certain rules. In the concept of literary language, the concept of norm is a basic concept. The norm is the state and possibility of using language units in the speech process that are accepted, approved and understandable by the members of the society. B. N. Golovin: "Norm is a practical feature of language construction, created by the people who use it due to the need for mutual understanding of language units. It is this need that makes people want to favor one option and abandon another in order to achieve the unity of the language system. Together with the society's aspiration to achieve such unity, the language norm in the national literary language rises to a high level and becomes stronger. The norms of the Uzbek literary language are classified in scientific works as follows: 1) lexical-semantic norms - lexical (word usage) norms; 2) pronunciation (orphoepic) norms; 3) accentological (correctness of accent in words and forms) norms; 4) phonetic (use of speech sounds) norms; 5) grammatical (morphological and syntactic) norms; 6) word formation norms; 7) spelling norms; 8) writing (graphics) norms; 9) punctuation norms; 10) methodological ying norms within the Uzbek language in two parts: 1. General norm or general norm of the language. 2. Private norms of the language or private norm. The general norm consists of the sum of the system of norms used in all forms of a certain language, for example, the Uzbek language. A specific norm is a specific manifestation of the general norm in the forms of speech,

forms, and forms of the language. Based on the above analysis, we can talk about the following specific norms of the Uzbek language:

- 1) norm of the Uzbek literary language;
- 2) norm of Uzbek dialects and dialects (dialectal norm);
- 3) Uzbek colloquial speech norm;
- 4) social networks of the Uzbek language, i.e. "social dialects", norm of "social slang" (slangs, professional speech forms, norms specific to other types of slang).

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